

A generic route of hydrophobic doping in hole transporting material to increase longevity of perovskite solar cells

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SUMMARY

The use of hydrophobic dopant is paramount for the success of organic semiconductors. Here we demonstrate, the use of *N*-heterocyclic hydrophobic ionic liquid, 1-butyl-3-methylpyridinium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide (BMPyTFSI) to induce dual functionality; as p-type dopant as well as additive for state of the art Spiro-OMeTAD hole transporting material (HTM). This ionic liquid doped HTM was then implemented for perovskite solar cells fabrication and gave competitive results. The dopant has the ability to substitute state-of-the-art ultra-hygroscopic lithium salt (LiTFSI) and problematic 4-*tert*-butylpyridine (*t*-BP) additive. BMPyTFSI was found to increase the conductivity of Spiro-OMeTAD, and its usage as dopant in HTM reduces charge recombination, improves the film formation by reducing the pinholes on HTM surface, and allows to fabricate efficient devices. Competitive air stability of solar cells in comparison to their state-of-the-art dopant was found, and these findings open up to a broad range of organic semiconductors for hydrophobic ionic liquid-based doping.

KEYWORDS: ionic liquid, perovskite solar cells, hydrophobic dopant, air stability

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CONTEXT & SCALE

The government commitment towards carbon neutral energy source, has made photovoltaic main contender for cost competitive and portable source of energy. Currently, the photovoltaic market is being dominated by silicon technology which has reached grid parity. With, the increasing appetite for renewable energy thin film photovoltaic technology will gradually rise its market share. Solution processed perovskite solar cells have made stunning progress in a very short time frame, though they also suffer from intrinsic issues. Device long-term stability, triggered by thermal and moisture induced degradation, remains a challenging task. Here we present the use of a hydrophobic ionic liquid which can act as a ubiquitous dopant for the hole transport materials such as Spiro-OMeTAD and can rival the usage of state of the art dopant. This generic route can be applied to other organic semiconductors to increase the number of charge carriers, and prevent the degradation of the underlying water-sensitive perovskite layer.

INTRODUCTION

The societal appetite for green and clean technology, which should be innovative and cost effective, has allowed to reinvent perovskites materials for photovoltaic applications. Perovskites have made stunning progress in the field of thin film photovoltaics due to their appealing features such as low cost fabrication, low materials usage, tunable band gap and ambipolar charge transport.¹ The cumulative efforts of researchers led perovskite-based solar cells to exhibit unprecedented rise in power conversion efficiencies (PCE), increasing from mere 3.8% by Kojima et al. in 2009² to an astonishing value of 22.7%, recently achieved at KRICT.³ With the accomplishment of such a rapid progress, the most appealing aim is to develop cost effective fabrication process and importantly demonstrate decent stability in a prolonged outdoor conditions to sustain IEC61215 test.^{4,5} The architecture of perovskite solar cell (PSCs) is made up of a thick layer of perovskite, acting both as light harvester and charge transporter, sandwiched between charge selective contact i.e. electron-blocking, hole transporting layer (HTL) and electron-transporting layer (ETL). The HTL remains ubiquitous and one of the important component to influence the photovoltaic parameters.^{6,7} The state-of-the-art 2,2',7,7'-tetrakis(*N,N*-di-4-methoxyphenyl-amine)-9,9'-spirobifluorene (Spiro-OMeTAD) is the most studied and efficient hole transporting material in PSCs.⁸ Spiro-OMeTAD in its pristine form shows low hole mobility and poor conductivity due to its bulky tri-dimensional structure causes large intermolecular distance. This low charge carrier mobility and low conductivity will increase series resistance and causes significant

charge recombination in devices. To address such issues, doping of HTL is a prerequisite for device fabrication.^{9,10} Typically, p-type dopants are used, which are constituted of molecules with relatively high electron affinities and can generate unpaired electrons in the organic matrix through stable charge transfer complexes.

Lithium-bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI) was introduced by Graetzel and Snaith in 2006¹¹ to increase the conductivity and shifting of the quasi-Fermi level of the holes to a lower level. Lithium salts do not directly oxidized Spiro-OMeTAD, but rather promote light catalyzed redox reactions in presence of O₂, this leaves free hole in the matrix and by doing so, it increases the conductivity by almost three orders of magnitude, along with an enhancement in hole mobility¹². Due to the ultra-hygroscopicity of lithium salts, it will absorb moisture from atmosphere and implicates a moisture induced degradation of HTL layers as well as the underlying perovskite, compromising the stability of devices. 4-*tert*-butylpyridine (*t*-BP) is also used as additives in HTL to suppress the recombination of photogenerated electrons, increasing the polarity of the HTM and allows improving the open circuit voltage. However, *t*-BP is a polar solvent, which accelerates the deterioration of perovskite and is partially liable for the device instability. Furthermore, several Cobalt (Co) complexes were developed with the debut of FK102 by Graetzel in 2011¹³⁻¹⁵ to further enhance the conductivity of Spiro-OMeTAD. This Co complex was used as an additional additive for Spiro-OMeTAD oxidation to achieve acceptable level of conductivity and efficient device fabrication. Both the LiTFSI and *t*-BP was found to have adverse effect on the hysteresis and stability of devices. The hysteresis not only originates from the unbalanced charges, non-radiative decays (losses), or poor interfacial contacts but also from the dopant employed.

Here in, we put forward, ionic liquid based hydrophobic dopant for Spiro-OMeTAD, which can rival the usage of conventional tri-component (LiTFSI+*t*-BP+FK109) based dopant and achieved similar level of photovoltaic performance, but with improved stability.

Ionic liquids are widely investigated for electrochemical applications¹⁶ due to their remarkable properties, such as ionic conductivity, high viscosity, high hydrophobicity, high thermal stability and tunable solvent properties. They have been also used as p-type dopant in small molecules or conjugated polymers based organic semiconductors.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ Among them, we have found that, pyridinium-based air and water stable ionic liquids represent a well-known class of hydrophobic materials suitable for opto-electrical devices as dopant.^{19,20} Hydrophobicity, negligible vapor pressure, high ionic conductivity, and high thermal stability c.a. 300-400°C, are viable merit for electronic applications.^{21,22} We report the use of a *N*-heterocyclic ionic liquid as a generic hydrophobic p-type dopant for HTL. The use of 1-butyl-3-methylpyridinium

bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide (BMPyTFSI) as a hydrophobic dopant increases the conductivity of Spiro-OMeTAD by two orders of magnitude and allows to fabricate moisture stable and efficient devices. The effect of the BMPyTFSI doping content on the photovoltaic performance and device long-term stability was systematically studied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Molecular structures of BMPyTFSI and Spiro-OMeTAD are shown in Figure 1A. BMPyTFSI consists of a large cation and a weakly co-ordinated anion, the cation comprises of butyl and methyl alkyl chain linked with one pyridinium group, while anion is bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide($\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_2\text{-N-CF}_3\text{SO}_2$) encompasses of two intense electron-withdrawing groups CF_3SO_2 -bonded with nitrogen through S-N-S bonds.²¹

To elucidate BMPyTFSI doping effect on Spiro-OMeTAD, various concentration of BMPyTFSI was used for Spiro-OMeTAD doping. For comparison purposes, pristine Spiro-OMeTAD, as well as Spiro-OMeTAD doped with LiTFSI and *t*-BP and with or without FK209 was also studied.

To exemplify, whether BMPyTFSI works as p-type dopant and oxidizes the Spiro-OMeTAD, the UV-visible absorbance measurements were made on pristine and doped solution of Spiro-OMeTAD. It is well known²²⁻²⁴ that p-type doping of organic semiconductor results in the formation of oxidized species, evident by the evolution of new absorption band in the visible region between 400-700 nm. To note here, for acceleration of the oxidation process, Spiro-OMeTAD/BMPyTFSI solution was activated under illumination ($100\text{mW}/\text{cm}^2$) at ambient atmosphere up to 30 min.

Figure 1B depicts the UV-visible absorption spectra of Spiro-OMeTAD in chlorobenzene at different illumination time with 7.8 mol% BMPyTFSI as a dopant. The UV-visible absorption spectra of Spiro-OMeTAD with other studied molar concentrations of BMPyTFSI is reported in supporting information Figure S1.

The addition of BMPyTFSI to the Spiro-OMeTAD solution shows characteristic absorption peaks of neutral Spiro-OMeTAD between 300-400 nm while minor changes in the region of 450-800 nm (black line, 0 min) occurs. Subsequently, Spiro-OMeTAD solutions containing various amount of BMPyTFSI, or classical dopants (LiTFSI and *t*-BP) were illuminated for 5,10,15, 20 and 30 min sequentially and absorption spectra were recorded to identify the extent of oxidation. A clear rise in the absorption band intensity at 520 nm up to 30 min and a simultaneous decrease of the band intensity at 308 and 389 nm was observed with increment of time. The presence of peak at 520 nm indicates the formation of mono-cation radical of Spiro-OMeTAD due to partial oxidation by BMPyTFSI, and it is in accordance with previous reports.^{13,23,25,26} The increased absorption intensity at 520 nm implies the increased number of oxidized Spiro-OMeTAD

(increase in concentration of oxidized species) until the saturation point occurs and indicates that BMPyTFSI works as a p-type dopant instead of catalyst. The dependence of absorption signal on illumination time suggests that photons are participating to induce oxidation of Spiro-OMeTAD in ambient condition.

For comparison purposes, in similar condition, absorption spectra of Spiro-OMeTAD using conventional dopant and additives such as LiTFSI (50 mol%), *t-BP* (330 mol%) was also measured under illumination. The results exhibit similar spectral trends and evolution of a peak at around 520 nm. The oxidized Spiro-OMeTAD can be marked by the presence of absorption band at 520nm, which is absent in the case of ground state Spiro-OMeTAD. However, LiTFSI+*t-BP* doped samples showed less dependency to the exposure time with respect to the ionic liquid dopant. (Figure S1).

The evidence of oxidation process can also be visualized by naked eye (Figure 1C-E). The visual pictures were recorded after the preparation of doped solution (BMPyTFSI with Spiro-OMeTAD) and pale dark yellow color was noted without any illumination, indicating that onset of oxidation starts even in the absence of light and a low intensity absorption band appears at around 520 nm in visible part of the spectrum (Figure 1B, black line, 0 min). This yellow color transforms into dark brown color within 5 minutes and becomes more pronounced on 20 min illumination (Figure 1C-E). The change in color appears due to the increased concentration of oxidized Spiro-OMeTAD, which will subsequently shift Fermi level.

Figure 1F depicts the effect of BMPyTFSI concentration on Spiro-OMeTAD under light illumination for 30 min. In case of pristine Spiro-OMeTAD, absorption bands at 308 and 389 nm were observed only, no new absorption band appears in the visible region even after exposure to the light. Contrary to this, when BMPyTFSI was added to the Spiro-OMeTAD solution, a clear growth in the absorption band at 525 nm and simultaneous decrease of the band intensity at 308 and 389 nm was observed with increasing BMPyTFSI concentration. Similar spectral features were also observed for other dopant/additive such as LiTFSI/*t-BP*²⁴, and Cobalt (III) complex doping^{13,23} (Figure S2)

The peak intensity at 525 nm increases up to a certain molar concentration i.e. 7.8 mol%, pointing towards the more number of neutral Spiro-OMeTAD are converting to oxidized Spiro-OMeTAD⁺. Beyond this concentration, the peak at 525 nm decreases with increasing the BMPyTFSI concentration suggesting the saturation in the generation of oxidized species.

These results suggest, that BMPyTFSI can works as a p-type dopant for Spiro-OMeTAD as a result of photo-induced oxidation and the doping efficiency can be improved upon

exposure to white light illumination.^{27,28} Fig.1G proposes the oxidation process through the ball and stick model. The following process may occur during the oxidation process to achieve equilibrium

Where $(\text{BMPy})_x\text{O}_y$ stands for 1-butyl-3-methylpyridinium oxide, and the Spiro is weakly bounded to delocalised anion of ionic liquids i.e. TFSI in this case.

To further probe the p-type doping effect of BMPyTFSI on Spiro-OMeTAD, two-probe electrical conductivity measurements were made using linear sweep voltammetry experiments as reported in the literature^{11,24} and details are summarized in supporting information. For this, various amount of BMPyTFSI was added to the HTM solution and illuminated under white light ($100\text{mW}/\text{cm}^2$) for 30 min prior to spin coating. Figure 2A shows the I - V characteristics of spun coated layers of BMPyTFSI doped Spiro-OMeTAD, and conductivity was calculated from the slope of I - V plot using the ohm's law. Figure 2B shows the dependence of the Spiro-OMeTAD conductivity on BMPyTFSI content. The calculated conductivity of pristine Spiro-OMeTAD was 4.9×10^{-8} S/cm, this value shows increment by two orders of magnitude upon addition of 5.3 mol% BMPyTFSI and reached a value of 1.2×10^{-6} S/cm. The conductivity also showed the steady enhancement and reached the maximum at 7.8 mol% BMPyTFSI (4.40×10^{-6} S/cm) and beyond this, the conductivity starts to drop by an order of magnitude for the 12.3 mol% BMPyTFSI (4.67×10^{-7} S/cm). It is notable that the trend of conductivity values are in accordance with the absorption measurements (Figure 1F & Figure S3). The conductivity of LiTFSI doped Spiro-OMeTAD showed a value of 4×10^{-5} S/cm at very high doping concentration (50 mol% with respect to Spiro-OMeTAD), while in the case of BMPyTFSI, very low concentration (7.8 mol%) of dopant was used and is effective in reducing the charge transport resistance of Spiro-OMeTAD. These values of conductivity for pristine and LiTFSI doped Spiro-OMeTAD are in agreement with the literature.^{14,24} It is known that the pyridinium based ionic liquids are considered to be a combination of Brønsted acid-base and can assist the oxidation of Spiro-OMeTAD, while the cation induces electrostatic force between ionic species and thus increase the conductivity by increasing the hole concentration.¹⁴

To examine further doping effect, we have performed electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy on pristine, BMPyTFSI doped and conventional doped Spiro-OMeTAD. Pristine Spiro-OMeTAD gave a very weak signal, while conventional and BMPyTFSI doped Spiro-OMeTAD presented very intense and symmetrical signal

(Fig.2C). Due to the higher concentration of oxidized Spiro-OMeTAD⁺ with BMPyTFSI, it gave relatively strong signal and confirms the formation of radical cation. The weak coordination nature of BMPyTFSI, will result in fast electron transfer by oxidizing the Spiro-OMeTAD. Furthermore, we have performed ¹H-NMR spectroscopy measurements of Spiro-OMeTAD in pristine, conventional and BMPyTFSI doped ones. In the case of Spiro-OMeTAD with conventional dopant very sharp and distinct peak were obtained along with the characteristic Spiro-OMeTAD peak of 3.7 (s, OMe), 6.9-6.7 (fluorene) and 7.5 (Ph), however in the case of BMPyTFSI doped Spiro-OMeTAD relatively broad and deformed peaks were obtained (Figure S4).

In general, the broadening of peaks suggests exchange between environments or H-bond formation. Here we speculate this can be due to the increased concentration of Spiro-OMeTAD⁺ species. Downward shift in the spectrum of BMPy⁺ was observed in the presence of Spiro-OMeTAD, which can be due to opening of charge transfer process (oxidation) between BMPy⁺ to ground state of Spiro-OMeTAD.

Photovoltaic Performance and Stability

To elucidate the influence of dopant behavior on photovoltaic parameters, four different concentrations of BMPyTFSI in Spiro-OMeTAD were screened for PSCs fabrication. (FAPbI₃)_{0.85}(MAPbBr₃)_{0.15} or MAPbI₃ was used as a light harvester, and was prepared using one step deposition method followed by solvent engineering approach. Solar cells were prepared with a configuration of fluorine doped tin oxide(FTO)/ compact TiO₂ (40nm) / mesoporous TiO₂ (150 nm) + perovskite (600nm) / Spiro-OMeTAD (170 nm)/ Au (80 nm). The cross-sectional scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of the champion device encompasses of 7.8 mol% BMPyTFSI doped Spiro-OMeTAD with (FAPbI₃)_{0.85}(MAPbBr₃)_{0.15} as perovskite layer is shown in Figure 2D. All the layers can be clearly differentiated and a very intimate interface between perovskite capping layer and Spiro-OMeTAD can be observed.

Figure 3A shows the *J-V* curves measured under AM1.5G simulated sun light (100mW/cm²), and the corresponding photovoltaic parameters are listed in Table 1. The reference device, fabricated with pristine Spiro-OMeTAD gave poor performance and a PCE of 4.50%, with a short-circuit current density (*J*_{sc}) of 17.62 mA/cm², open circuit voltage (*V*_{oc}) of 940 mV and fill factor (*FF*) of 27.27% was achieved. The relatively low PCE of pristine Spiro-OMeTAD based device was attributed to the low *FF*, arising due to the low conductivity and high charge transport resistance in the Spiro-OMeTAD, which in turn led to a high series resistance.¹³ The devices doped with BMPyTFSI showed better performance than the pristine Spiro-OMeTAD based devices (reference device).

The devices using 5.3 mol% BMPyTFSI dopant showed competitive PCE of 12.60%. A significant improvement in photovoltaics parameters, from $V_{OC} = 940$ mV, $J_{SC} = 17.62$ mA/cm² and $FF = 27.27\%$ (for pristine Spiro-OMeTAD device) to 990 mV, 21.69 mA/cm² and 58.68% (5.3 mol% BMPyTFSI) was observed respectively. For 7.8 mol% BMPyTFSI loadings, the FF improves significantly up to 65.12%. With further increase in the BMPyTFSI loadings, i.e. 10.1 mol% and 12.3 mol% of BMPyTFSI, a decrease in the FF was noted, which is in accordance with the conductivity trend (Figure 2B). The usage of BMPyTFSI (5.3 mol%) increases the J_{SC} to 21.69 mA/cm², and this decreases slightly for the high doping concentration. We have found that the Spiro-OMeTAD, doped with BMPyTFSI (7.8 mol%) exhibited the optimum concentration for fabrication of solar cells and yielded a PCE of 14.06%, which was on par in performance with the solar cells fabricated using conventional doped and additivated Spiro-OMeTAD (PCE = 14.26%) (Table 1). Notably, the molar percentage in the conventional doped Spiro-OMeTAD is astonishingly high, especially in the case of LiTFSI and *t-BP* that corresponds to 50 mol% and 330 mol% respectively; on the contrary the molar percentage of the hydrophobic BMPyTFSI dopant used in this work was very low (5.3-12.3 mol%), with an optimized value of 7.8 mol%. The low doping level of the Spiro-OMeTAD is a prerequisite for improving the overall performance of the solar cells.^{29,30} In fact, the low doping level used for Spiro-OMeTAD is found to be beneficial for device long term functioning and stability,³¹ as the Li based ionic dopant can migrate to the perovskite and accelerate the degradation⁵.

In spite of being employed in such a low percentage of doping, BMPyTFSI addition led to an enhancement in the V_{OC} of about 80 mV compared to the un-doped devices and strikingly, the optimized concentration (7.8 mol% BMPyTFSI) showed the best performance. This device gave similar value of V_{OC} (1020 mV) as of conventional LiTFSI and *t-BP* doped devices (1040 mV). It is well known that in case of dye sensitized solar cells, the difference between the quasi Fermi level of the TiO₂ and HOMO of the HTM determines the V_{OC} .^{32,33} Upon doping, the downward shift of Fermi level in HTM occurs as a result of additional hole density. Thus, the difference between the quasi Fermi level of TiO₂ and Spiro-OMeTAD Fermi level increases and yield high V_{OC} . Upon further increasing the doping concentration, minute decrease in V_{OC} was recorded from 1020 to 1000 mV possibly due to low conductivity, which will reduce hole concentration. To acquire further insight about the interfacial charge recombination behavior of PSCs using various dopants, dark current was measured for different doped devices as shown in Figure S5 and the values of series resistance (R_S) and the shunt resistance (R_{SH}) of devices are presented in Table 1. The lower dark current density and late turn-on of the

device in dark was observed for the optimum doping concentration of BMPyTFSI (7.8 mol%), compared to the undoped, and this was further confirmed by the relatively higher value of shunt resistance ($R_{SH} = 1317.65 \text{ ohm.cm}^2$) reflecting lower leakage current. The low leakage current and late turn-on of the BMPyTFSI doped device in dark allows to decrease the rate of charge recombination^{33,34} (Figure S5). In all likelihood, the pyridinium based ionic liquids dopant in Spiro-OMeTAD matrix reduces the charge transport resistance with the photoactive layer by increasing the conductivity and also diminishes the charge recombination at TiO_2 /perovskite interface in the similar fashion as *t-BP* does.^{14,20} Devices were also fabricated using MAPbI_3 as light harvester, Spiro-OMeTAD as HTM with conventional dopant and with 7.8 mol% BMPyTFSI. The devices fabricated with conventional dopant gave a PCE of 15.8 %, while the device fabricated with 7.8 mol% BMPyTFSI yielded a PCE of 13.8% (Figure S6A). These values can be further optimized. Both the devices were subjected to maximum power point tracking for a period of time and no noticeable changes were observed (Figure S6B), in terms of drop in performance.

To probe further, if the absorption of oxidized Spiro in visible region at 520 nm affects the perovskite absorption and this in turn influences short circuit current, UV-visible absorption of perovskite samples with structure $\text{FTO/c-TiO}_2/\text{mp-TiO}_2/\text{perovskite/HTL}$, was measured using integrating sphere in transmission mode. It can be deduced from Figure S7 that BMPyTFSI doped Spiro-OMeTAD devices exhibit increased perovskite absorbance intensity in the visible range compare to perovskite without the HTL. Thus, we ruled out the decrease in J_{sc} was due to the competition of light harvesting between perovskite and oxidized Spiro-OMeTAD species.

Figure 3B illustrates the incident photon-to-current conversion efficiencies (IPCEs) spectrograms and their corresponding integrated J_{sc} of the devices are shown at secondary Y-axis of Figure 3B and also documented in Table 1. A broad plateau was observed over the whole visible spectral range from 300 - 800 nm for all the devices. The maximum IPCE was observed in case of the optimized concentration (7.8 mol% BMPyTFSI), where >85 % of the incident photons are converted. The calculated integrated photocurrent from the IPCE spectrum are in accordance with the measured short circuit current (J_{sc}) from J - V characterization with a deviation up to 3% (Table 1). To observe the hysteresis effect in devices, J - V curves were recorded in forward and reverse bias for the devices and hysteresis index was calculated (Figure S8). Figure S9 shows the trend of hysteresis index for different concentration of BMPyTFSI and conventional dopants. The level of hysteresis decreases with the increase in concentration of BMPyTFSI. This can be argued due to the ion migration control, by

eliminating the use of lithium salt and also due to increased uniformity and smoothness of the HTL with less number of pinholes when BMPyTFSI was used, which favors the formation of an improved interface between the HTL and the perovskite layer. This hypothesis was further supported by the images recorded with the help of optical microscope and SEM of the HTL surfaces doped with different concentration of BMPyTFSI (Figure S10 & S11). It also points towards the role of BMPyTFSI to improve the quality of film formation and minimizing the pinholes.

In order to understand the bulk and interfacial recombination processes in the fabricated devices, the electrochemical Impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was employed. EIS provides information about different internal processes occurring in the PSCs at diverse operating conditions and can separate interfacial and bulk processes. By means of EIS, several resistive and capacitive processes arising in the device on different time scale, either in the bulk or at interfaces, including charge transport, recombination and slow ionic processes (at low frequencies) to which hysteresis is also correlated can be elucidated. We have analyzed devices fabricated from different dopant, and to understand the recombination kinetics under white light excitation, Nyquist plots of impedance spectra were investigated (Figure S12). Figure 3C shows the electron recombination resistance extracted by fitting the impedance response under white light illumination to a simple $R_S-(R_{LF},-CPE_1)-(R_{HF},-CPE_2)$ equivalent circuit, where a constant phase element (CPE) replaces an ideal capacitor to obtain a better fitting. From Figure 3C, it can be deduced, at voltages close to the V_{OC} , Spiro-OMeTAD doped with conventional tri-component (LiTFSI+*t*-BP+FK109) based dopant represents a highest recombination resistance (R_{rec}), i.e. better charge extraction and superior device performance, while BMPyTFSI doped devices represent higher R_{rec} than LiTFSI + *t*-BP doped ones. It is known fact that capacitance in PSC generally dominated by the geometrical component, which can be expressed as; $C_g=\epsilon\cdot\epsilon_0\cdot A/d$, where ϵ is the dielectric constant of the perovskite, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, the effective contact area and d is the thickness of the absorber layer. From the slope in curve, the β -parameter can also be extracted, for which a value of $\beta = 0.5$ for (Spiro-OMeTAD + LiTFSI + *t*-BP), and $\beta = 0.37$ (Spiro-OMeTAD + BMPyTFSI) was obtained.

Figure 3D shows that the capacitance value extracted from the high frequency component is constant at applied voltage close to V_{OC} which is in agreement with its geometrical nature.

The main purpose of employing hydrophobic dopant is not only to achieve similar photovoltaic performance, but to increase the longevity of the PSCs by preventing them from environmental moisture attack. The photovoltaic properties of the doped devices were periodically monitored for a long period of time (> 200 days), and the effect of

BMPyTFSI doping on device stability was investigated. The un-encapsulated devices were kept in humidity chamber (50%RH) in dark conditions, and results are shown in Figure 4A. Under these conditions, the devices fabricated from BMPyTFSI exhibits an improved stability than the standard ones, and they are able to maintain up to 80% of the initial efficiency for more than 7 months in humid (50%RH) condition. The devices encompass BMPyTFSI exhibited a loss in efficiency of only 20% in over seven months of monitoring, while the conventional doped Spiro-OMeTAD based devices display a drop of over 50% of the initial efficiency. The V_{OC} and FF remained largely constant over the period for the hydrophobic dopant-based devices, while significant drop was observed for the J_{SC} , and is accountable for the loss in efficiency. Figure 4B depicts the comparison of PV parameters with deviation for the devices using different dopant for Spiro-OMeTAD.

To further demonstrate the effective hydrophobic and moisture blocking property acquired by the usage of BMPyTFSI to the Spiro-OMeTAD, contact angle measurements were carried out to the un-doped, conventional doped and BMPyTFSI doped HTL deposited atop of the perovskite (Figure 5). Expectedly, the contact angle value for the BMPyTFSI doped layer was $>90^\circ$ while the conventional doped layer showed a lower value of $>78^\circ$. We have observed that the values of the incident angle increases linearly with the increase in BMPyTFSI concentration. Furthermore, the contact angle value remains constant over the period of time with respect to both the pristine and conventional doped Spiro-OMeTAD films.

Additionally, full devices prepared using different doping agent for Spiro-OMeTAD were kept outside in natural sunlight in a humid environment ($>50\%RH$) and monitored for a month. This can be followed from the photographic images shown in Figure S13, the degradation of the perovskite layers is quite visible for the conventional doped Spiro-OMeTAD based device, while the BMPyTFSI doped ones remained almost unchanged, demonstrating how the air and water stable ionic liquid based hydrophobic dopant effectively works as moisture protective agent for the perovskite toward the humidity exposure. Devices were fabricated employing different dopant concentration and also subjected to compare with conventional dopant and additives i.e. FK209 and LiTFSI+*t-BP*. The average value of photovoltaic parameters with the standard deviation are reported in Table S1. We have also noted the reproducibility for BMPyTFSI doped devices were better than of LiTFSI+*t-BP* doped devices.

Conclusion

We have employed a hydrophobic ionic liquid-based dopant, BMPyTFSI which effectively works to tailor the charge transport and surface properties of Spiro-OMeTAD. The results obtained from electro-optical and spectroscopy measurements, clearly indicates that BMPyTFSI doped Spiro-OMeTAD, oxidizes to Spiro-OMeTAD⁺, and the electrical conductivity of oxidized Spiro-OMeTAD increases by two orders of magnitude upon optimal doping of BMPyTFSI.

The effect of doping level on photovoltaic performance and longevity of Spiro-OMeTAD based perovskite solar cells was systemically investigated and devices doped with 7.8 mol% BMPyTFSI showed on par efficiency as of devices fabricated using conventional tri-dopants LiTFSI+*t*-BP+FK209. Notably, BMPyTFSI doped devices exhibited superior long term stability, when un-encapsulated devices exposed to sun or under >50% relative humidity for few months of monitoring.

By employing such a low percentage of hydrophobic and water impermeable BMPyTFSI as dopant, the un-encapsulated devices can be controlled for degradation. BMPyTFSI was found to be a multifunctional additive in perovskite solar cells. This represents an alternative and generic approach, which can be utilized on a range of organic semiconductors as a hydrophobic dopant. We believe the elimination of ultra-hygroscopic LiTFSI and low vapor pressure based *t*-BP additives in perovskite solar cells, will facilitate and pave the way for its exploitation for commercial purposes.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material and Methods

Chemicals were procured from either Sigma Aldrich or Agros and were employed as such. Spiro-OMeTAD represented as 2,2',7,7'-tetrakis(*N,N*-di-*p*-methoxyphenylamine) - 9,9-spirobifluorene (Spiro-OMeTAD) was purchased from Merck KGaA, while methylamine iodide, CH₃NH₃I (MAI) and formamidinium iodide (FAI), was purchased from Dyesol while PbI₂ was obtained from (TCI). 1-butyl-3-methylpyridinium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (BMPyTFSI) was procured from Ionic Liquids Technologies GmbH (IoLiTec).

Device fabrication:

Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) were fabricated on FTO-coated glass (TEC, Pilkington) patterned by laser etching. Before any deposition, the substrates were cleaned using Hellmanex solution and rinsed with deionized water and ethanol. After this they were ultrasonicated in acetone, rinsed using ethanol and 2-propanol and dried through compressed air. TiO₂ compact layer was deposited by spray pyrolysis at 450 °C using

1 mL of titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetyl acetonate) precursor solution (75 % in 2-propanol, Sigma Aldrich) in 19 mL of pure ethanol using oxygen as carrier gas. After the blocking layer deposition (TiO_2 compact layer), the substrates were kept for further 30 minutes at 450 °C for the formation of anatase phase. Once the samples achieved room temperature, they were treated with TiCl_4 (dipping in a 0.02 M TiCl_4 solution in deionized water at 70°C for 30 minutes) with the aim to obtain a homogenous layer. Next, the samples were washed with deionized water, burned at 500°C for 10 minutes and were cooled down to room temperature. After this, a TiO_2 mesoporous layer (Dyesol, 30NRD) was deposited by spin coating (4000rpm for 30 s with 2000 rpm seconds⁻¹ as acceleration) and the samples were annealed by heating them up progressively to 450°C for 2 hours. Atop of this, perovskite ((FAPbI₃)_{0.85}(MAPbBr₃)_{0.15}) was deposited by one step method as reported in reference. 1.4 M mixture of lead iodide (PbI₂), lead bromide (PbBr₂) and a mixture of formamidinium iodide (FAI) and methyl ammonium bromide (MABr) were mixed in a solvent mixture of *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) and dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO). The solution was prepared inside an argon glove box under moisture and oxygen-controlled conditions (H₂O level: <1 ppm and O₂ level: <10 ppm) and kept stirring at 80°C overnight in order to dissolve PbI₂ completely. The deposition of the perovskite was carried out by a one-step method following solvent engineering. In this method, the perovskite precursor solution was spin-coated on top of the mesoporous layer at 1000 rpm for 10 seconds and then 6000 rpm for 30 seconds. During the second step, chlorobenzene was dripped at the center of the substrate in the last 20 seconds. After solvent treatment, the films were transferred onto a hotplate and annealed at 100°C for 60 minutes. For MAPbI₃, Stoichiometric precursor solutions (1.25 M) were prepared by mixing MAI (Sigma Aldrich) and PbI₂ (TCI) in *N,N'*-dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO). The perovskite layers were then fabricated by using a two-steps spin-coating process, first step 1,000 r.p.m. for 10s; second step 3,500 r.p.m for 30 s. During the second step 110 µl of chlorobenzene were poured onto the films 10s prior to the end of the program, and then substrates were annealed at 100°C during 40 min.

HTM preparation

For the hole transporting material, Spiro-OMeTAD was used by dissolving 72.3 mg in 1 mL of chlorobenzene. 1-butyl-3-methylpyridinium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (BMPyTFSI) ionic liquid was used as a dopant/additive for Spiro-OMeTAD. The stock solution of ionic liquid was prepared by adding required amount of BMPyTFSI in acetonitrile. HTL solutions were prepared by adding different amounts of this ionic liquid stock solution into the 72.3 mg/mL Spiro-OMeTAD solution to obtain 0, 5.3, 7.8, 10.1 and 12.3 mol% of BMPyTFSI respectively. For comparison, the standard-doped solution of Spiro-OMeTAD was prepared by dissolving 72.3 mg of Spiro-OMeTAD in 1mL of

chlorobenzene, and adding as standard additives 17.5 μL of a lithium bis (trifluoromethylsulphonyl)imide (LiTFSI) stock solution (520 mg of LiTFSI in 1 mL of acetonitrile), 21.9 μL of a FK209 (Tris(2-(1H -pyrazol-1-yl)-4-tert-butylpyridine)-cobalt(III)Tris(bis(trifluoro-methylsulfonyl)imide))) stock solution (400 mg in 1 mL of acetonitrile) and 28.8 μL of 4-tert-butylpyridine (*t-BP*). Then 35 μL of each HTM solution were dropped on the perovskite substrates of the solar cell samples described above and the samples were spin coated at 4000 rpm for 30 seconds. Following this, 80 nm of gold was used as cathode which was thermally evaporated atop of HTL under a vacuum level between 1×10^{-6} and 1×10^{-5} torr.

Characterization

The absorption spectra of Spiro-OMeTAD solution in chlorobenzene were acquired using 1 cm cuvette with various concentration of BMPyTFSI and also for Spiro-OMeTAD. Absorption spectra of perovskite with HTLs was also measured in transmission mode using Perkin Elmer UV-vis-NIR lambda 1050 spectrophotometer with 160 mm integration sphere. Surface morphology and cross-sectional images were obtained using Hitachi S-4800 field emission scanning electron microscope at power 2 kV.

The samples for conductivity measurements were prepared on FTO coated glass substrates with a thin layer of TiO_2 deposited atop of it. Followed by this, Spiro-OMeTAD solution (oxidized or neutral) were spun coated. DC (direct current) conductivity (σ) at room temperature in dark, was determined from the slope of I - V plot, $I = \sigma \frac{A}{d} V$, where A is area of sample (0.16 cm^2) and d is thickness of sample. The thickness of the different doped sample was determined by cross sectional SEM images.

The NMR experiments were carried out on a Bruker AV500 spectrometer, equipped with a 5 mm BBI probe and gradients on the Z axis, operating at a frequency of 500 MHz for proton using DMSO-d_6 as solvent. Data acquisition and data processing was carried out with the TOPSPIN 2.1 software (Bruker). The pulse sequences used were the Bruker standard. The chemical shifts have been referenced with respect to the residual solvent signal. Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR) spectra were recorded on Bruker EMX (ER-510-QTresonator) spectrometers under continuous wave in solution form

Current density–voltage (J – V) curves were recorded with a Keithley 2400 source-measurement-unit under AM 1.5 G, 100 mW/cm^2 illumination from a certified Class AAA, 450 W solar simulator (ORIEL, 94023 A). Light output power was calibrated using a NREL certified calibrated mono-crystalline silicon solar cell. A black metal mask (0.16 cm^2) was used over the square solar cell active area (0.5 cm^2) to reduce the influence of scattered light. The IPCE measurements were performed using a Newport 150 W xenon lamp coupled to an Oriel Cornerstone 260 motorized $\frac{1}{4}$ m mono-chromator as the light

source, and a 2936-R Power Meter to measure the short circuit current. Electrochemical Impedance spectroscopy (EIS) studies were made with the help of Bio-logic (SP-300), under illumination of a warm white LED over a range of DC light intensities. Frequency response of the solar cells at different positions of the Fermi level, was fixed by the DC illumination intensity (open circuit voltage) to avoid voltage drop. A 20 mV perturbation step in the range 2MHz–1mHz was used to obtain the spectra. Following the measurements, the data were fitted with the help of Z-view software to extract the characteristic parameters of the devices.

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

Supplemental information includes thirteen figures and one table, and can be found with this article online at

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

LC made the experiments and prepared first draft, MSM assisted in device fabrication and EIS data analysis, SK performed electro-optical and spectroscopy measurements, supervised and coordinated the research. S.A provided the concept, supervised and directed the research. All authors contributed to the completion of the final document.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests, however a patent was filed in 2016 with publication number WO/2017/178674 and assigned to Abengoa. Abengoa is a multinational company and has significant interest in the renewable energy sector.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Molecular Structure, Absorbance Spectra, Visual Pictures and Ball & stick Model.

(A) Chemical structure of Spiro-OMeTAD and 1-butyl-3-methylpyridinium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide (BMPyTFSI).

(B) UV-vis absorption spectra of Spiro-OMeTAD at different illumination time using 7.8%mol BMPyTFSI; showing evolution of the new peak at around 520 nm and responsible for partial oxidation of Spiro-OMeTAD. The inset shows the enlarged spectra of the oxidized Spiro-OMeTAD peak at around 520 nm.

(C-E) Visual picture acquired for the Spiro-OMeTAD doped with conventional dopant and different amount of BMPyTFSI before and after 20 min light exposure to 1 sun illumination showing the evident color change of the solution.

(F) UV absorption spectra of Spiro-OMeTAD solution in chlorobenzene with different molar concentration of BMPyTFSI. Each doped solution was illuminated under white light for 30 min for the generation of oxidized Spiro-OMeTAD. The inset shows the zoomed

region around 520 nm peak showing partially oxidized Spiro-OMeTAD. All solutions contained the same concentration of Spiro-OMeTAD (1.5×10^{-5} M);
(G) Ball and stick model to show the oxidation process in Spiro-OMeTAD.

Figure 2. Conductivity, EPR Spectra and Microstructure of Spiro-OMeTAD
 (A) Semi logarithm plot of I - V characteristics of spin coated Spiro-OMeTAD films doped with different molar concentration of BMPyTFSI relative to HTM.
 (B) Electrical conductivity derived from the Figure 2A as a function of BMPyTFSI content. (The solutions concentration of Spiro-OMeTAD (1.5×10^{-5} M) were kept constant and the doped solution was illuminated under white light for 30 min for the generation of oxidized Spiro-OMeTAD before spin coating.
 (C) EPR spectra of Spiro-OMeTAD doped with different dopant.
 (D) Cross sectional SEM image of a typical device with 7.8 mol% BMPyTFSI doped Spiro-OMeTAD with $(\text{FAPbI}_3)_{0.85}(\text{MAPbBr}_3)_{0.15}$ as light harvester.

Figure 3. Electrical Properties of Fabricated Devices

(A) J - V curves of devices prepared with Spiro-OMeTAD using different concentration of BMPyTFSI, or the conventional dopant and with undoped Spiro-OMeTAD.

(B) Incident photon-to-current conversion efficiency (IPCE) and their corresponding integrated current of the best devices using different dopant.

(C) Recombination resistance as a function of open-circuit potential, extracted from fittings of the impedance spectra for MAPbI_3 based devices.

(D) High frequency capacitance as a function of open circuit voltage of the MAPbI_3 based PSCs using different doping agents.

Figure 4. Performance and Statistics of Perovskite Solar Cells.

(A) Evolution of photovoltaics parameters of the devices containing Spiro-OMeTAD doped with different concentration of BMPyTFSI and conventional dopant. These devices were kept in dark and under humidity (>50%RH) and were timely monitored.

(B) Comparison of the photovoltaics parameters with standard deviation of the best devices using different dopant for Spiro-OMeTAD. The stars represent the maximum value, the dots the average, and the box lines represent the 25, 0 and 75th percentiles in the distribution.

Figure 5. Surface Properties of Doped Spiro-OMeTAD

Contact angle measurements were made by dropping the water droplet on Spiro-OMeTAD layers doped with different concentration of BMPyTFSI and conventional dopant. The HTMs were deposited atop of perovskite films. The resulted angle is the average of three different measurements, and each measurement have been made at t=0 min, while putting the water droplet and after 3 min from the drop fall.

TABLES

Table 1. Photovoltaics parameters extracted from *J-V* curve for the champion cell under 100 mW / cm².

HTM composition	J _{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V _{oc} (mV)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	R _s (ohm.cm ²)	R _{sh} (ohm.cm ²)
Spiro+BMPyTFSI	21.69	990	58.68	12.60	9.88	730.59
5.3 mol%	(21.01) ^b					
Spiro+BMPyTFSI	21.17	1020	65.12	14.06	7.53	1317.65
7.8 mol%	(21.11) ^b					
Spiro+BMPyTFSI	21.12	1000	57.91	12.24	10.39	918.54
10.1 mol%	(20.90) ^b					
Spiro+BMPyTFSI	20.74	1000	58.90	12.19	10.16	676.34
12.3 mol%	(20.37) ^b					
Spiro+LiTFSI+ <i>t-BP</i> ^(a)	19.42	1040	70.22	14.26	4.03	4964.25
	(18.95) ^b					
Spiro+LiTFSI	21.37	950	73.45	14.96	4.24	1269.15
+FK209 ^(a)	(20.92) ^b					
Spiro only	17.62	940	27.27	4.50	48.70	103.01
	(13.43) ^b					

^a The molar concentration of LiTFSI, FK209 and *t-BP* used here was 50 mol%, 10 mol% and 330 mol% respectively relative to Spiro-OMeTAD. ^b Integrated photocurrent values from IPCE measurements.